

A. APPENDIX

A.1. Sound Pressure Level (SPL) Informed Sampling

We discuss the details of SPL informed sampling, which we mentioned in Section 4.2.1. In addition to collecting 10-second audio recordings, each SONYC sensor also measures SPL. From each 10-second snippet, 1-second sliding windows with a hop size of $\frac{1}{2}$ -second, each containing 8 SPL values are extracted, yielding 20 audio frames and 160 SPL values per recording.

We aggregate all SPL values that overlap with an audio frame’s timestamp, say time i to j , by taking their mean as shown in Equation 1. Note that we compute the mean after converting the SPL values (in dB) to linear scale.

$$\bar{x} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{j - i + 1} \sum_{k=i}^j 10^{SPL_k/10} \right) \quad (1)$$

In order to discriminate audio frames that correspond to a potential “noise event”, we find frames with “relatively” higher SPL values using the following procedure. We divide 24 hours into 2-hour bins yielding 12 bins per day. The SPL values of audio frames in each bin are statistically ranked, $rank(\bar{x})$, and then normalized by dividing with the total number of entries in the bin. These normalized values, referred to as *relevance scores*, are used to determine *relative loudness*.

For M bins with N audio frames in each, we thus have a relevance score matrix, $S \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$. The j^{th} audio frame in i^{th} 2-hour

bin would have the entry as in Equation 2.

$$S[i, j] = \frac{1}{N} rank(\bar{x}_j) \quad (2)$$

Finally, we convert the relevance score matrix, S , corresponding to a 24-hour day into probability distribution by dividing each element by the number of elements in the matrix.

A.2. Downstream Classifier

The CNN featurizer and downstream classifier is run on each audio frame described in Appendix A.1. The downstream classifier consists of a fully-connected layers and an output layer with 8 nodes, corresponding to the 8 coarse-labeled classes in the dataset. Since SONYC-UST is a multi-label rather than a multi-class classification task, the output nodes use *sigmoid* activation function.

The output from all the slices are aggregated using *Autopool* [1] over time dimension to yield the final classification of the 10-second audio snippet.

B. REFERENCES

- [1] B. McFee, J. Salamon, et al., “Adaptive pooling operators for weakly labeled sound event detection,” *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 2180–2193, 2018.